

ECONOMICS OF PRODUCTION OF BRINJAL IN NAGPUR DISTRICT

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(MS Received: 02.02.2023; MS Revised:03.03.2023; MS Accepted:04.03.2023)

MS 3014

(RESEARCH PAPER IN ECONOMICS AND STATISTICS.)

Abstract

Brinjal is one of the most important fruit vegetable crop. It contribute good in income of brinjal growing farmers and also in states/ countries economy. Along with economic value it also have good medicinal and nutritional properties. India is having second rank in brinjal production followed by China. The study has based on cost structure, returns and profitability during the year 2021-2022 based on primary data. The study was conducted in Nagpur, Hingana and Kuhi tahsils were selected purposively having maximum area and production of vegetables. Four villages were selected from Nagpur and three villages selected from Hingana and Kuhi tahsil total 10 villages were selected for the present study. A sample of 35 brinjal growers were selected based on random sampling. Twelve growers were selected from Nagpur and Hingana tahsils and eleven growers were selected from Kuhi tahsils. The study's main purpose was to estimate cost, returns and profitability of brinjal production. It was observed that, per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal at cost C₃ i.e.Rs. 141454.25. The average yield and gross returns per hectare increased with increased with the increase in size of farms. The input output ratio of Brinjal at cost C₃ was 1:2.34. This indicates that, Cultivation of brinjal crop was economically profitable. The average main production was 275.89 qtl/ha.

Key words: Brinjal, cost, returns, profit, input-output ratio

Introduction

Vegetables are important constituents of Indian agriculture and nutritional security due to their short duration, high yield, nutritional richness, economic viability and ability to generate on-farm and off-farm employment. Vegetables are vital sources of proteins, vitamins and minerals, dietary fibers, micronutrients, antioxidants and phytochemicals in our daily diet. India continues to the second largest producer of vegetables in the world next to china. However, the horticulture sector has witnessed tremendous growth as a result of investment through National Horticulture Mission (NHM) and a number of other programmes.

Brinjal or eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) is an important solanaceous crop of sub-tropics and tropics which is low in calories and fats, contains mostly water, some proteins, fiber and carbohydrates. It is good source of minerals and vitamins. Brinjal is known to have ayurvedic medicinal properties and is good for diabetic patients. (Mayuri Raut and et.al 2020). The area under brinjal in Nagpur district 2026.25 ha with production of 7320.00 tonnes in 2020-21.

Materials and Methods

The standard cost concepts i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ were used in present analysis.

Cost A₁: All variable cost excluding family labour cost and including depreciation.

1. Value of Hired human labour (HL)
2. Value of hired and owned bullock labour (BL)
3. Value of hired and owned machine labour (ML)
4. Value of seeds
5. Value of insecticides and pesticides
6. Value of manure
7. Value of fertilizers
8. Irrigation charges

9. Depreciation on implements and farm building
10. Land revenue, cesses and other taxes
11. Interest on working capital
12. Miscellaneous expenses

Cost A₂: Cost A₁ + Rent paid for leased-in land

Cost B₁: Cost A₁ + interest value of owned fixed capital assets

Cost B₂: Cost B₁ + rental value of owned land

Cost C₁: Cost B₁ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₂: Cost B₂ + imputed value of family labour

Cost C₃: Cost C₂ + 10 % of Cost C₂ on account of managerial functions

performed by farmers.

Gross and net returns**Gross returns**

Gross returns of the farmers under the present study was estimated from returns obtained from sale of main produce.

Gross returns = Value of main produce + Value of by produce

Net returns

Net returns were computed at different costs i.e. Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by deducting respective costs from the gross returns.

Input-Output ratio

It was calculated at cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂, and Cost C₃ by dividing gross income by respective cost.

Results and Discussion**Cost of cultivation of selected Brinjal growers**

The cost of cultivation is helpful for crop planning therefore in order to know the cost, returns and profitability, the cost of cultivation of selected Brinjal growers were worked out.

Per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal growers

The per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal growers were workout and presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal growers

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ Ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3		4	5	6	7
1	Hired human labour	Male	Days	49.21	250.00	12302.50	8.69
		Female	Days	98.41	180.00	17713.80	12.52
	Subtotal					30016.30	21.21
2	Bullock labour		Days	3.10	365.00	1131.50	0.79
3	Machine charges		Hrs	4.65	425.00	1976.25	1.39
4	Seeds		Gm	363.79	10.00	3637.90	2.57
5	Manure		CL	15.95	400.00	6380.00	4.51
		N	Kg	102.06		612.36	0.43

6	Fertilizers	P	Kg	49.91		399.25	0.28
		K	Kg	51.22		614.63	0.43
	Subtotal					1626.24	1.14
7	Irrigation charges					777.67	0.54
8	Plant Protection					3977.49	2.81
9	Incidental charges					261.91	0.18
10	Repairing charges					364.73	0.25
11	Working Capital					50149.99	35.45
12	Interest on working Capital at @ 6% per annum					3008.99	2.12
13	Depreciation					1962.74	1.38
14	Land Revenue					299.89	0.21
15	Cost A₁					55421.61	39.17
16	Rental Value Leased in land					-	-
17	Cost A₂					55421.61	39.17
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @10%					5487.86	3.87
19	Cost B₁					60909.47	43.05
20	Rental Value of Land					54878.61	38.79
21	Cost B₂					115788.08	81.85
22	Family human Labour	Male	Days	24.99	250.00	6247.50	4.41
		Female	Days	36.44	180.00	6559.20	4.63
	Subtotal					12806.70	9.04
23	Cost C₁					73716.17	52.11
24	Cost C₂					128594.78	90.90
25	10% Cost C₂					12859.47	9.09
26	Cost C₃	Rs	ha			141454.25	100
27	Main produce	Rs	ha	275.89	1200.00	331068.00	
28	Per quintal cost of Production	Rs	qtl			512.71	

Table 1 revealed that, the per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal at cost A₁, cost A₂, cost B₁, cost B₂, cost C₁, cost C₂ and cost C₃ were Rs. 55421.61, Rs. 55421.61, Rs. 60909.47, Rs. 115788.08, Rs. 73716.17, Rs. 128594.78 and Rs. 141454.25 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards cost 'A₁' and cost 'A₂' (39.17 per cent) In cost 'A₁' share of seed was 2.57 per cent, hired human labour 21.21 per cent, bullock labour 0.79 per cent, manure 4.51 per cent, fertilizers 1.14 per cent, indicating that all the above

Table 2: Per hectare cost, returns and profitability from Brinjal

inputs are cash inputs. The cost 'B₁' contributes to 43.05 per cent, cost 'B₂' contribute 81.85 per cent. The share of family labour was 9.04 per cent. The per hectare yield obtained by brinjal growers was 275.89 quintals with gross return of Rs. 331068.00. In case of brinjal crop, the per quintal cost of production was Rs. 512.71.

Per hectare cost, returns and profitability from Brinjal

The per hectare cost and returns of the brinjal growers was worked out and presented in Table 2.

(Rs/ha)

Sr.No.	Particulars	Brinjal
1.	Main produce (q/ha)	275.89
2.	Value of main produce	331068.00
3.	Gross Returns	331068.00
4.	Cost of cultivation at	
	Cost A ₁	55421.61
	Cost A ₂	55421.61
	Cost B ₁	60909.47
	Cost B ₂	115788.08
	Cost C ₁	73716.17
	Cost C ₂	128594.78
	Cost C ₃	141454.25
5.	Net returns	
	Cost A ₁	275646.39
	Cost A ₂	275646.39
	Cost B ₁	270158.53
	Cost B ₂	215279.92
	Cost C ₁	257351.83
	Cost C ₂	202473.22
	Cost C ₃	189613.75
6.	Input-output ratio	
	Cost A ₁	5.97
	Cost A ₂	5.97
	Cost B ₁	5.43

	Cost B ₂	2.85
	Cost C ₁	4.49
	Cost C ₂	2.57
	Cost C ₃	2.34

Table 2 indicates that the per hectare production of brinjal growers was 275.89 quintals. The gross returns from brinjal was Rs.331068.00. Whereas the cost of cultivation at C₃ of brinjal has been estimated to be Rs. 141454.25. The per hectare net returns at cost C₃ received by brinjal was Rs.189613.75. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for brinjal was 1: 2.34.

The input-output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and it indicates that the brinjal registered a good input-output ratio was 1:2.34 it means the hypothesis is acceptable. It indicates that the Brinjal cultivation was profitable.

Conclusions

The average main production was 275.89 qtl/ha. It is observed that per hectare cost of cultivation of Brinjal at cost C₃ was Rs. 141454.25. the gross returns from brinjal was Rs. 331068.00. The average yield and gross returns per hectare increased with the increase in size of farms. The input-output ratio at cost C₃ for brinjal was 1: 2.34. This indicates that, cultivation of brinjal was economically profitable.

References

1. **Bala, B., Sharma, N. and Sharma, R.K. 2011.** Cost and return structure for the promising enterprise of off-season vegetables in Himachal Pradesh Agril. Econ. Res. Revi, 24:141 – 148.
2. **Meshram, R. R., N. V. Shende and S. D. Kathale, 2015.** Cost of Benefit analysis and marketing of Brinjal Vegetable in Bhandara District. *Asian Resource*. 4(4):85-92.
3. **Nandeshwar, N., S. Jagannath, T. Pritesh and M. Shashikumar, 2013.** Economics of production and marketing of vegetables in Akola district. *Global Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Health Science*. 2(2):78-82.
4. **Raut M. and Khobarkar V. 2018.** Economics of production of Brinjal in Akola district. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*.
5. **Shedge R., S. Jagtap and S. Perne 2021.** Economics of cost and returns of brinjal in Ahmednagar district. *The Pharma Innovation journal* 10(12): 1877-1878.
6. **Thorat T. D. V.G Naik and R. A. Tasbi 2019.** Economics of cost returns and profitability in Ratnagiri district. *International Journal of Chemical studies* 7(5): 4400-4402.